

When Responsibility Enables Ethics Washing: *Responsible Realism* as a Critical Lens for Probing Institutional Recommendations for the Use of AI in Higher Education

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Abstract

This work introduces the notion of *Responsible Realism*, a theoretical resource we propose to characterize the stance in which Higher Education institutions acknowledge the harms and ethical problems of commercial AI, yet still promote its use, shifting the burden of mitigation onto individual end users by calling to “responsible use.” To clarify and exemplify Responsible Realism as an analytical lens, we follow the logic of critical case selection through an interdisciplinary analysis of several institutional guidelines for the adoption and use of (generative) AI in higher education. Through exemplary fragments we illustrate rhetorical moves and assumptions about commercial AI and its use, and probe the analytical reach of the concept of Responsible Realism against actual documentary material. Rhetorics of inevitability, technological determinism, and anthropomorphism offer the premises that underpin and serve as the backdrop against which Responsible Realism operates. Responsible Realism also necessitates prior discursive moves—ethics washing and critical washing—which decouple the acknowledgment of risks and harms from any obligation to act upon that acknowledgment. Altogether, by naturalizing fatalism and bypassing serious critical scrutiny in favor of *pro forma* engagement, genuine responsibility becomes unfeasible. Paradoxically, by transferring the lion's share of responsibility to the end users, institutions, simultaneously, and in an asymmetric exercise of power, insulate themselves from accountability while retaining the right to claim they acted responsibly by recommending responsible use. Furthermore, tech companies' accountability is also erased from the equation in the process. We conclude by calling the academic community to critically engage with guidelines and policies for the use of AI, and to reject narratives designed to dilute responsibility.

Keywords

Artificial intelligence, education, ethics washing, determinism, responsible realism

1 Introduction

Especially since late 2022 with the release of ChatGPT to the public, the pace for the adoption of the so-called “generative AI”¹ (genAI) in higher education by all parties (e.g. students, faculty, and administrators) is unprecedented. Not even the rapid adoption of Internet services and the web that happened during the 1990s compares to what is going on today. Because of this, and paraphrasing Marshall McLuhan (cited in Benedetti and DeHart 1997: 70), we are determined to understand what’s happening. Because we don't choose just to sit and let the *juggernaut* roll over us.

A terminological note before proceeding: Artificial Intelligence (AI) encompasses many things and meanings (Van Rooij et al. 2024), and very different technologies are often grouped under a single term. AI can thus mean everything and nothing at the same time, from a hodgepodge of algorithmic techniques over an AI subfield to a simulator of human conversation. This gives the impression that it concerns a homogeneous ecosystem, while this is certainly not the case. Seeking to be inclusive of for a non-technical readership and for reasons of space, we too adopt the umbrella term, acknowledging that further differentiation would be in order (cf. Guest et al. forthcoming: 6). Unless necessary for contrast, we will refrain from using “generative AI” as if it was a new category at the same level of “traditional AI” instead of a subtype thereof. There are technical differences, but these do not justify elevating a subtype to a new category.

In this essay, we seek to heed the call for critical reflection made by many scholars in the last years (Forbes and Guest 2025; Guersenzvaig and Sánchez-Monedero 2025; Guersenzvaig et al. forthcoming; Guest et al. forthcoming; Hartzog and Silbey 2025; Laird et al. 2025; Monett and Grigorescu 2024; Monett and Paquet 2025; Pearson 2025; Slater 2025; Watermeyer et al. 2024; Wieczorek et al. 2025; Williamson et al. 2024), who have warned about the socio-ethical risks and actual harms the uncritical adoption of AI technologies poses for higher education and scholarship. Amidst a mix of enthusiasm, fear, and faith in technological progress, many universities and national agencies for higher education seem to be running around frantically creating AI commissions and publishing all sorts of reports, recommendations, guidelines, and frameworks to try to navigate this maelstrom.

Problematizing institutional guidelines and documents for the use of AI is imperative as they adopt and reproduce a narrative marshalled by the Tech sector to persuade all parties involved (Whittaker 2021). As Guersenzvaig et al. (forthcoming) point out, this narrative turns the adoption of generative AI into an “unstoppable” force or even a *fait accompli*, sidelining reflection on its ethical and pedagogical appropriateness or even ignoring it completely. In the same spirit, Guest et al. (forthcoming) show how the terminological confusion surrounding what is deemed “intelligent” fuels illusory expectations and hinders critical thinking within the university.

In this article we identify, name, and develop the notion of Responsible Realism. At its simplest, Responsible Realism embodies a paradox. On the one hand, an institution or a person, against a backdrop of technological determinism and inevitability, acknowledges the risks and shortcomings of AI systems. And, simultaneously, on

¹ Under generative AI we understand computational models that, by combining probable sequences through symbol prediction, diffusion processes, or other methods, produce text, images, audio, and video from text-based instructions or other types of input known as “prompts.” ChatGPT, Copilot, and MidJourney are some examples of commercially available generative AI products.

the other, it encourages responsible adoption and use while delegating ethical responsibility to individual end users, eschewing systemic and structural issues, as well as collective responsibility.

Along these lines, and more specifically, we posit that Responsible Realism can serve as a theoretical resource not only for researchers but also for teachers, students, administrators, and policymakers seeking to reflect on and critically examine institutional guidelines and policy documents for the use of AI. Our intention is to encourage everyone in the academic community and society at large to adopt a reflective stance toward these documents—even before they are created—questioning their fraught assumptions and the narratives they, possibly inadvertently, promote. In this way, we seek to invite readers to pause and reconsider what may have already become a familiar yet unexamined habit of thought: treating AI as something they must inevitably grapple with.

A methodological note is in order: the development of the notion of Responsible Realism is part of a broader project that examines, reflects on, deconstructs, and demystifies institutional discourse on AI in higher education, drawing on an initial dataset of 39 publicly accessible institutional documents for the use of AI from 14 predominantly European countries compiled by the authors so far. This paper does not present the findings of that analysis but the conceptual apparatus developed for it. The central element of this apparatus is Responsible Realism, a notion that was developed gradually and inductively from repeated close readings and discussions through a bottom-up, broadly interpretive, multidisciplinary, theoretically informed analysis of the documentary material. Through this process, a coherent and recurring ideological pattern became apparent: AI was being framed as simultaneously fraught and unavoidable, and the ethical responsibility arising from this framing was being delegated to individual end users.

In order to clarify the notion of Responsible Realism and exemplify its applicability as an analytical lens, we cite and discuss several excerpts from the dataset throughout this paper.² Yet, the function of these fragments is heuristic and illustrative of the rhetorical moves and assumptions that we subsume under Responsible Realism. The excerpts included were selected not because they are typical but following the logic of critical case selection (see Flyvbjerg 2006): they were chosen not to achieve statistical representativeness but because they render the concepts under discussion with particular clarity and intensity, and it is precisely this explicitness that allows to probe the analytical reach of the concept against actual documentary material. That is, if the logic of Responsible Realism is made visible in the chosen excerpts, our claim is that it is also likely operative, albeit in less explicit form, across the broader field. Validating this claim, however, is a task for further investigations, whether quantitative or qualitative.

In this spirit, the quotations are offered neither as statistical evidence of the prevalence of Responsible Realism, nor as proof of a trend. Our analysis does not rely on the logic of representative sampling, and therefore we make no claims of statistical generalizability for our findings³—nor do we need to, given that our aim here is conceptual development rather than empirical mapping. We only claim analytic validity, and any

² We want to note that our aim is not to single out particular institutions but to flesh-out the narrative moves behind Responsible Realism and inevitability. It is also worth noting that the wording of some of the cited fragments may have changed or no longer be publicly available. The 12 guidelines and documents, from which 22 exemplary quotes were selected and included in this paper, were last consulted on December 3, 2025, and archival copies have been retained.

³ We do, however, expect the fragments to feel recognizable to readers acquainted with AI guidelines and policy documents, even where the specific phrasing varies.

generalizations we make are to be considered interpretive and analytical, the validity of which rests on their theoretical plausibility and cogency.

The paper proceeds as follows: in Section 2, we discuss the rhetoric of inevitability and the technological determinism that function as the backdrop against which Responsible Realism operates. The supposed inevitability of AI is pragmatically invoked by those we call *responsible realists* as a justification for presenting Responsible Realism as the only viable course of responsible action. Before discussing Responsible Realism in Section 4, Section 3 discusses ethics washing and critical washing, which are the broader categories within which it can be situated. Finally, Section 5 provides a conclusion.

2 Rhetoric of inevitability and technological determinism

The bedrock assumption of Responsible Realism is that AI adoption is inevitable. We begin by examining how, against a backdrop of technological determinism, AI is presented as inevitable and naturalized. This *rhetoric of inevitability* weakens the possibility of discussing ethical, pedagogical, and social issues *ex ante*. If the matter is presented as already occurring or having occurred, *ex ante* reflection makes little sense. This rhetoric, steeped in determinism, reframes corporate marketing as educational advancement and substitutes deliberation with adaptation.

Consider this fragment. (Quoted guideline fragments appear with a border around them to differentiate them from other cited text.)

Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as one of the most transformative technologies of our time and its influence extends to virtually all the fields we know. From healthcare to agriculture to transport to entertainment, AI is present in a variety of ways, optimising processes, improving efficiency, and enabling innovation on an unprecedented scale, sometimes inadvertently and without us even being aware that we are using it. (SMEVTS 2024: 2)

This claim, extracted from guidelines published by the Ministry of Education, Vocational Training and Sports of Spain, summarizes the kernel of the basic premise in the rhetoric of inevitability we want to examine. The gambit seems to be to appeal to a sensation that is floating in the air: the idea that AI is transforming “all the fields we know” in actuality. No evidence is marshalled to substantiate this claim, however. Exercising critical thinking requires us to go beyond the familiar sensation that “AI is changing everything” and ask whether this is actually the case.

As one of us has argued elsewhere (Guersenzvaig et al. 2025), the purpose of claims like these is not to describe reality but to impose it, transforming an expectation or a desire into a *fait accompli* that needs no further examination. Instead of asking what type of transformation we would want in these fields or if we want these fields to change at all, we are told that “all fields” are already changing. But using a software program is evidently not the same as transforming the field within which it is used.

AI systems are becoming an integral part of everyday life, education, and professional life. (UOS 2025, in German in the original)

Artificial intelligence is transforming the world. We sit on the cusp of a revolution on the scale of the development of the steam engine or the launch of the internet. (...) We are aware of the exponential

nature of change in this field and will remain committed to assessing its development and impact well beyond the statement we issue today. (IEU 2023)

AI is already a part (or currently being built into) all the common digital tools like Office 365, smartphones, search engines, translation tools etc. So there is no option for anyone to opt out or 'just ban AI' – we will all need to adapt to this new technology. (KUDK n.d.)

For the sake of argument, let's assume that the claims in these excerpts are true. There is an is-ought fallacy here and it involves going from a descriptive claim (AI has emerged as one of the most transformative technologies of our time and its influence extends to virtually all the fields we know, and AI-based applications are everywhere) to a normative claim (therefore, we must embrace this transformation). This is unwarranted and disguises ideology as logic. This move displaces the questioning of whether we want that transformation and obfuscates who is primarily benefiting from this supposed adoption by presenting the transformation as a natural force, which operates autonomously.

We will discuss the notion of responsibility in more detail below, but it is worth mentioning now that there is a strong functional connection between responsibility and the rhetoric of inevitability, which is detrimental to the former. This connection was famously identified by Joseph Weizenbaum (1976: 241, *Italics in the original*):

“The myth of technological and political and social inevitability is a powerful tranquilizer of the conscience. Its service is to remove responsibility from the shoulders of everyone who truly believes in it.

But, in fact, there *are* actors!”

Enchanted by determinism, some see the adoption and use of generative AI in education as inexorable as the effects of the laws of physics. This perspective nudges us towards helplessness and acceptance: no one can change gravity. Besides, it would be absurd to ask whether gravity is *good* or if we want it. The best we can do is grapple with it and move forward! Against this backdrop, equating AI with a fundamental force, the “question zero” is not being asked by the enchanted ones: their central point is not whether generative AI is desirable but how it must be deployed and used. But AI is nothing like gravity. These technological developments and their adoption are not driven by natural forces but by people, companies, and institutions holding particular values and willing particular futures: these are the actors Weizenbaum refers to. We must not be persuaded by the false premise of a human-made artefact being inevitable.

Compliance and acceptance

AI and research and development ... will become indispensable (Braun 2024: 2, in German in the original)

How do we teach for a future (or present) where AI is available to all? (KUDK n.d.)

The tone of certainty about AI inexorably playing a role in the future of education turns contingency into inevitability. Without a normative evaluation, this kind of language reinforces the idea of AI as a natural phenomenon rather than a deliberate human choice. Such certainty acts as a rhetorical anaesthetic: it numbs the reader's sense of responsibility, presenting compliance as the only rational response. Ursula Franklin (1999: 17) referred to this as the “enormous social mortgage [that comes with] prescriptive technologies”: “The

mortgage means that we live in a culture of compliance, that we are ever more conditioned to accept orthodoxy as normal, and to accept that there is only one way of doing ‘it’.”

70% of the responding Information and Computing Sciences teachers indicated that they expect to use GenAI tools in teaching practices in the future. A short inventory of teachers’ recent GenAI practices revealed only a limited application yet, which indicates the need for collecting and sharing knowledge on specific practices of using GenAI in Programming Education. (Köppe et al. 2024: 1)

The first part of this fragment functions as a normalization mechanism: the 70% figure does not merely describe current attitudes but quantifies compliance with what has already been framed as an inevitable force. The limited number of actual applications, juxtaposed with the large number of users who expect to use genAI, functions as the premise for the fallacious conclusion that collecting practices for integrating it in (programming) education is necessary. This, on the one hand, reflects the is-ought fallacy at work. On the other hand, it is a logical *non sequitur* in which the conclusion does not follow from the premises: collecting and sharing knowledge does not become necessary simply because a majority expects to use a technological product in the future. Even if we take the survey above at face value, the results show nothing more than an attitude about expected future behavior, which might well be the result of massive corporate propagandist efforts rather than the product of collective will formed through a rational debate about its pedagogical value.

ITU acknowledges that generative AI-tools will dominate workplaces of the future, so we continuously adapt to the changes and needs of society and businesses. (ITU n.d.)

Artificial intelligence (AI) is indisputably one of the key technologies of the future. (Baumhauer et al. 2024: 2)

These fragments rehash the logic of inevitability by presenting the future as a consummated fact. Indeed, when we accept technological determinism, the future is a done deal and we can talk about it matter-of-factly. The certainty functions in a normative way: it orders the acceptance of corporate products as educational infrastructure, thus obfuscating the need for debate and deliberation. For the convinced techno-determinist, just like for the Laplacean omniscient scientist, the present is the cause of its future. Why debate or challenge what cannot be otherwise? Only a fool would do that.

Yet, McLuhan’s (McLuhan and Fiore 1967: 25) famous dictum that “there is absolutely no inevitability as long as there is a willingness to contemplate what is happening” eloquently contradicts the techno-deterministic posture. No purported trajectory for the use or adoption of technology is truly predetermined but is contingent on how technologies are designed, financed, promoted, regulated, and—above all—adopted by individuals and collectives. The narrative of inevitability seeks to pre-emptively naturalize compliance with the emerging orthodoxy and to foreclose situated, critical deliberation and principled decision-making. Once we are willing to recognize this, determinism dissolves, and the trajectories not only for design of (educational) technologies but also for their adoption, adaptation, regulation, or rejection reopen as matters to be debated rather than accepted as non-negotiable—a position supported by vast scholarship in both the Philosophy of Technology and Science and Technology Studies (see e.g., Bijker et al. 1987; Feenberg 1999; Ihde 1990; Latour 1988; MacKenzie & Wajcman 1999; Verbeek 2011).

Weizenbaum (1976: 242) cites a paper “circulated by the director of a major computer laboratory of a major university” stating:

“...the computer *has been incorporating itself*, and will surely continue to incorporate itself, into most of the functions that are fundamental to the support, protection, and development of our society. Even now, *there is no turning back...*”

The paper’s exact date of publication is not given, but we can safely say that it was written at least 50 years ago. The deterministic outlook, however, matches today’s. Weizenbaum’s (1976: 242) scathing commentary is worth quoting as it is relevant today as then:

“There is not the slightest hint of a question as to whether we want this future. It is simply coming. We are helpless in the face of a tide that will, for no reason at all, not be stemmed. There is no turning back. Even the question is not worth discussing.”

We’ve been here before.

Institutional statements about the future adoption of technologies effectively advance corporate agendas. In his treatise on the history of industrial automation in the U.S. from the 1950s onward, David F. Noble (1984: xi) writes,

“Ratifying the status quo as necessary at this stage of development, technological determinism absolves people of responsibility to change it and weds them instead to the technological projections of those in command. Thus, if this ideology simplifies life, it also diminishes life, fostering compulsion and fatalism, on the one hand, and an extravagant, futuristic, faith in false promises, on the other.”

Thus, universities become, at best, unintentional allies of technological corporations, which, through experts and pundits, sell us a vision of the world and simultaneously present themselves as infallible authorities predicting the future. Both the predictions of experts and those of universities, unsurprisingly, align perfectly with corporate intentions and plans to reshape laws, institutions, and all spheres of human life. These predictions are narrative gambits that frame the future as objectively predictable in order to make their vision real, enabled by their immense economic and political power. In other words, their predictions, when they play out as foretold, are self-fulfilling prophecies.

Technological momentum

We reject the idea of technological determinism, but we are wary of corporate strategies promoting early lock-in because, as technologies become widespread, they gain *momentum* (Hughes 1994), and when this happens, technology reversal becomes more difficult, not because it is an autonomous force, but because infrastructure, companies and institutions, regulations, the media, professions, markets, and our very own social and individual habits have coalesced around it. Think of cars.

Institutionally endorsed adoption can build a *momentum* that later makes technologies hard to undo. This is not to say that reversals are impossible; they aren’t, as shown, among other cases, by the phasing out of asbestos as insulation material in construction and ship building (see e.g., Council EU 2023; USEPA 2024). Reversals can and do happen, but it is indisputable that it would have been easier and far less tragic if the warnings about the extremely harmful effects associated with asbestos, known since the end of the 19th century (Frank and Van Zandwijk 2023), had been taken into account and incorporated in regulation and professional best practices before its use and irreversible harms started to grow exponentially in the 1950s. We believe we find ourselves at a similar juncture now with AI in higher education.

We are not arguing that AI is carcinogenic, but that it is gaining *momentum*. Narratives about technological determinism and exaggerated capabilities in machines—as well as anthropomorphism, a topic we will cover below—are intentionally chosen to get actors of the educational sector (educators, school and university managers, students, etc.) on board the AI bandwagon, something they have historically done fast and with ease (Postman 1995). Grandiose claims about the longstanding illusion of “teaching machines” have been around for decades in the education sector (cf. Watters 2021) but when such narratives are a genuine *copy&paste* from corporate AI's marketing and are enforced or promoted top down, then it is not expected they find much resistance coming bottom up.

We are not exaggerating. Tech companies provide all sorts of ready-made “resources” to universities, which leaders and administrators can use, such as the AI Communication Kit, that includes “A clear, actionable roadmap to help you launch ChatGPT Edu at your university” (OpenAI 2025), and also templates to announce ChatGPT to all stakeholders. This is the beginning of the one for faculty,

“Hi team,

We’re thrilled to announce that ChatGPT Edu is now available at [University Name]! AI is evolving rapidly, and this is an ideal time to explore how ChatGPT can support your teaching and research. Whether you’re designing coursework, preparing lectures, or diving into complex data analysis, ChatGPT can help generate new ideas, summarize academic materials, and streamline administrative tasks.” (OpenAI 2025)

The similarities with the language and claims of many university guidelines are striking but unsurprising. If any, there seems to be more willingness to serve corporate AI than to question its interference in education matters and goals (Postman was more than prescient in the 1990s!).

3 Ethics washing and critical washing

Besides taking place against the fatalistic backdrop of technological determinism discussed above, the paradoxical stance we call Responsible Realism also necessitates a prior discursive move which decouples the acknowledgment of risks from any obligation to act upon that acknowledgment. This decoupling is not unique to AI discourse in higher education, but belongs to a broader phenomenon whereby institutions and corporations manage the tension between the pursuit of technological and commercial interests, on the one hand, and the growing demand for ethical accountability, on the other. A well-known and related practice in the corporate world is *greenwashing*, whereby companies present themselves as environmentally responsible through selective disclosure and misleading communication while continuing practices that are harmful to the environment (cf. de Freitas Netto et al. 2020). Two other *pro forma* practices that are particularly relevant for our purposes are ethics washing and critical washing, which decouple symbolic rhetoric from substantive action. Since we take Responsible Realism as a specific variant of these broader categories, we need to situate these two practices first.

Ethics washing can be defined as the practice of instrumentalizing ethical language “as an acceptable façade that justifies deregulation, self-regulation or market driven governance, [which] is increasingly identified with technology companies' self-interested adoption of appearances of ethical behavior” (Bietti 2021: 267). Such practices are not unique to industry, but have also been extended to other sectors and ethical issues different from regulation and governance (Metzinger 2019). In essence, this practice allows for obscuring unethical practices and harms. As a consequence, “ethics is seen as the ‘easy’ or ‘soft’ option” (Wagner 2019: 84) to

avoid accountability, responsibility, and regulation (Ochigame 2019), and also as a way to purposely shape how ethics applied to technology (e.g. to AI) should be considered, and with, by, or for whom (Gerdes 2022).

Another decoupling behavior, *critical washing*, is a “[c]ritical reflection without appropriate action” (Suárez et al. 2025) and an especial case of ethical washing more common to the academic sector. Suárez and coauthors (2025) alert, “Reflecting on the harms of AI is not itself harm reduction. It may even contribute to rationalizing, normalizing, and enabling harm.” What is sold as having potential and benefits for users and companies alike is ripe with marketing rhetoric and proven harms, especially to already disadvantaged populations (Ajuzieogu 2025; Benjamin 2019; Birhane 2023; Eubanks 2019; Hao and Seetharaman 2023; McQuillan 2023; Wilkins 2025).

Examples of ethics washing and critical washing can be found in AI guidelines and corporate texts. Those harms are not reflected upon before the technology is used, however, but *a posteriori*, if at all.

AI systems can prove to be useful tools for scientific work, provided that users are aware of the potential risks and use AI in an acceptable and appropriate manner. (UOS 2025, in German in the original)

Even instructing a chat system to formulate its output concisely and precisely can have a positive impact on the carbon footprint. (UOS 2025, in German in the original)

The use of AI tools must be compatible with the principles of equality and equal opportunity. Any form of discrimination by AI systems must be ruled out. All users should critically reflect on the effects of AI. (HWR 2025: 9, in German in the original)

The first fragment is puzzling, if not outright fallacious. AI systems are either useful or not depending on the tasks they are designed to accomplish, how they are used, and the rate of success with which they accomplish those tasks. Those tasks are explicitly programmed, or a tool is used in ways that go beyond its originally intended design, to solve certain problems in certain situations or environments using certain resources. What is certain is that software does not become useful because users “are aware” of its externalities. What is more, being aware of risks doesn’t change programming instructions, or clean the data, or produce any new resource to be used by the software or hardware on which it runs or which it controls. Being aware of the thousands of data workers who, under conditions of precarity and psychological toll, annotate the data with which language models are trained (Hao 2025), does not have any effect in alleviating the miserable conditions under which they work. It is difficult to conceive an ethical use of such a technology when it is based on unethical practices. Promoting an *a posteriori* ethical use of a technology doesn’t rectify its intrinsic problems, nor releases its creators or its users from being accountable and responsible for the harms it causes; it only ignores them thereby shifting the focus to other more convenient matters. Any institutional narrative that accommodates or obscures these harms rather than addressing or avoiding the tools that exacerbate them is, in the most precise sense, ethics washing.

Similarly, there is no way a software can be used without being inefficient in some ways (energy to power the computers and servers and data centers where the programs and models and data are used; water to cool the servers and data centers when they heat; natural resources that are needed to produce the chips and raw materials with which computers are fabricated, human labor to deal with all that, etc.). From an environmental justice perspective, harms are not evenly distributed, as the ecological and social costs of resource extraction, energy use, and environmental degradation disproportionately affect already vulnerable and marginalized

communities (Hao 2025; Jiménez Arandia 2025; Luccioni et al. 2024; Parshley 2024). Thus, unless we contemplate a perpetual motion machine as a serious possibility, there is no way that using software which already consumes such amounts of resources can generate a net positive effect on the very resources it has already consumed and continues to consume. Considering resource consumption from an ethical perspective, the issue of whether something is wasteful concerns assessing whether the level of consumption is justified in relation to the purposes pursued and the outcomes achieved. When assessed against the current state, namely its largely speculative potentialities and its prevalent trivial or unnecessary uses, it is hard not to conclude that this type of software is wasteful.

Furthermore, many applications of data-intensive AI techniques, particularly generative AI, have repeatedly been shown to be dehumanizing (Akingbola et al. 2024; Bender 2024), extractivist and exploitative (Mejías and Couldry 2024; Muldoon et al. 2024), biased (Birhane et al. 2024), and to promote illegal (FBI 2024) and unethical practices (Fergusson et al. 2024; Köbis et al. 2025). From the very moment generative AI-based programs and models are used, the principles of equality and equal opportunity of those exploited to clean, annotate, or moderate the data were violated; the same occurs with the work and intellectual property of those whose creations were appropriated without their consent to train the models (Goetze 2024). Reflecting on the harms means nothing after the technology was already introduced in the classroom (Monett and Paquet 2025); analyses *a posteriori* do not reduce or avoid the harms, but perpetuate them.

Anthropomorphism as an ethical dead end

Anthropomorphism is a common cognitive and cultural phenomenon. We can in principle treat anything—from fish to smartphones to bacteria, or even rivers—as if it had beliefs, desires, understanding, and other human capabilities and traits. When we do this, we adopt the intentional stance toward an entity (Dennett 1989). Daniel Dennett (1989: 22) offers clear examples related to objects,

“[T]he chess-playing computer will not take your knight because it knows that there is a line of ensuing play that would lead to losing its rook, and it does not want that to happen. More modestly, the thermostat will turn off the boiler as soon as it comes to believe the room has reached the desired temperature.”

Who hasn't tried to verbally cajole a stalled car into starting or said that their laptop “decided” to update at the worst moment? These, however, are weak versions of anthropomorphism in the form of “as if” metaphorical reasoning used as a pragmatic predictive strategy. Most of us don't *really* believe that talking to our car will help start it.

However, Epley, Waytz, and Cacioppo (2007: 867) posit that even *very weak* versions of anthropomorphism “can still have a powerful impact on behavior, with people behaving toward agents in ways that are consistent with these metaphors.” What is more, even a small sensory cue can trigger anthropomorphism, “Adding a humanlike voice to a machine might make it seem more like a person” (Schroeder and Epley 2016: 1428). If even minimal cues trigger social responses, what can we expect from systems that simulate fluid, seemingly coherent, conversational exchanges with humans on purpose and in real time?

We believe anthropomorphism in genAI is more ethically problematic than when we say, for instance, that our printer is being “stubborn,” because the contextual conditions to foster this tendency when using chatbots have become engineered, i.e. hardcoded, into the interactional style these systems are designed to follow. Attributing human capacities to a machine is the result of a structural feature of generative AI systems,

different from the anthropomorphization people engage in of their own accord (Dennett 1989), based on their knowledge, motivation, and stimulus features (Epley et al. 2007; Schroeder and Epley 2016). Take for example ChatGPT’s feature to customize its “personality,” which is designed *precisely* to instantiate anthropomorphism:

“A personality is the style and tone ChatGPT uses when responding to you. It is a combination of traits, voice, and behavior that *shapes how answers feel*, whether that is *friendly and casual, concise and professional, or something else entirely.*” (OpenAI n.d., emphasis added)

Related research by Waytz et al. (2010) describes several effects of anthropomorphism such as increased credibility, trust, agency attribution, and even moral concern. By presenting an interface structured around first-person dialog messages plagued by social cues such as apologies and performative politeness, users are subtly primed to unwittingly project human traits—like intentionality, empathy, emotion, or agency—onto what is merely a software artifact with none of these traits.

Anthropomorphism is exacerbated by the type of effective prompting users are encouraged to use:

To refine the level of teaching/explanation, this practice could be combined with a persona prompt, for example: “From now on, act as computer science teacher teaching programming in xxx at bachelor level.” (White et al. cited in Köppe et al. 2024: 1)

Users are advised to interact with the system *as if it was* a person, thus compelling a dialog with a machine that accepts its *ersatz* alterity. This technique is often recommended for effective “prompt engineering” (see e.g. OpenAI 2023). Assuming the quality of the outcome is contingent on using this type of language, encouraging users to interact with the system in this way feeds a feedback loop of enchantment and deception.

That users anthropomorphize chatbots is not new. The phenomenon, known as the “ELIZA effect” (Hofstadter 1995; Turkle 1984: 41f) in reference to the first chatbot, was already described by Weizenbaum (1976: 7): “I had not realized ... that extremely short exposures to a relatively simple computer program could induce powerful delusional thinking in quite normal people.” In 1966, at the time of designing ELIZA, Weizenbaum and his team at MIT were not aware of the delusional behavior that would arise out of the first-person interaction style of the interface they were working on. But 60 years later, developers can’t claim plausible deniability about commercial products such as ChatGPT or Claude triggering this reaction—i.e., the ELIZA effect—in many users. This raises many ethical concerns because, as we described above, users often attribute human traits to systems that cannot genuinely support those expectations. This misplaced attribution can lead people to disclose sensitive information, rely on advice the system is not qualified to give, or form emotional attachments that make them vulnerable and that they might not be aware of.

In the literature, however, analyses abound that explain why AI algorithms (of any form, but especially in the form of chatbots or language models) are not and cannot be partners, nor tutors, or collaborators, or friends in the sense we humans deal with relationships of care and social interactions without risking dehumanization (Bender 2024; Caulfield 2025; Chen et al. 2023; Dang and Liu 2025; Flenady and Sparrow 2025; Kim and McGill 2024). We don’t have the space here to address this topic in full, but it suffices to say that a tutor, unless we devalue the term, must be capable of responding with genuine empathy, personal investment, moral judgment, and accountability, something systems like ChatGPT or Claude are not capable of. Yet, they are nonetheless marketed as “personal tutors,” and the first-person relational interaction is intended to suggest comprehension and create a sense of reciprocity. This creates a potential structural form of deception: the interface invites precisely the kind of bi-directional engagement that the system is fundamentally incapable of

supporting (Park et al. 2024; Simon 2025; Tarsney 2025). There is also the added risk of sycophancy (cf. Hill and Valentino-DeVries, 2025), which refers to the model programmed to give exaggeratedly agreeable or flattering responses instead of offering the critical guidance that is paramount in a tutoring context.

For Shannon Vallor (2024), this dynamic becomes especially troubling because current AI systems do not just trigger misattributions of intelligence, empathy, or creativity, but—by functioning as a mirror—actively reflect back to us the very ideals we are already primed to see. As Vallor (2024: 133–134) puts it,

“When we gaze in our AI mirrors at the words and images they generate, at the predictions and classifications they make, we are not seeing objective truths, under any definition of “objective.” We are seeing reflections of what humans valued enough to describe or record in data. But not *all* humans. What our AI mirrors show are the values of those humans who have historically had the power to shape the dominant patterns now engraved in our recorded data.”

Vallor’s “AI mirror” compounds the ELIZA effect by reinforcing our natural disposition to interpret fluent language as signs of understanding, “supportive” text as signs of empathy, or pixels arranged according to statistical functions as signs of creativity. The interaction style of genAI systems thus exploits not only our cognitive heuristics but also deeper values and expectations about, for instance, intelligence, empathy, or creativity. But whose intelligence? And what counts as empathy? As Vallor suggests, the reflections, i.e., the system’s output, are shaped by dominant voices and norms embedded in the training corpus. The mirror thus both reflects and distorts everyone’s values.

Because the way this interaction style could interfere with users’ autonomy, choice, and decision-making, this type of interaction could arguably be characterized as a “deceptive pattern,” a common term within technology practitioners, scholars, and policy-makers that broadly understood refers to “tricks used in websites and apps that make you do things that you didn’t mean to, like buying or signing up for something” (Brignull et al. 2023). The term and protections against them—also called “dark” patterns—are enshrined in different laws all over the world. For instance, the EU Digital Services Act describes them as “practices that materially distort or impair, either on purpose or in effect, the ability of recipients of the service to make autonomous and informed choices or decisions” (EU 2022: Recital 67). Importantly, in this context, the rule does not require deceptive intent for a practice to count as deceptive; its effects alone are sufficient.

Anthropomorphism is not just an unintended effect of genAI but a designed feature. The simulation of understanding, empathy, concern, and first-person interaction seeks to lower resistance and maximize user engagement. The ethical problem is not only that users may be misled by the interaction style, though they often are, but that the interaction itself has been manufactured to inherently engage with human emotions in a way they should not (see Veliz 2023). Deception and the instantiation of false intimacy are not flaws that can be fixed through greater awareness but a strategic goal of those who design and deploy these systems. Asking users to engage with such systems “responsibly” and “critically” is therefore to ask them to navigate a situation that is already ethically fraught. This is ethics and critical washing in the strictest sense: the harms and risks are not institutionally addressed, for instance by rejecting systems that simulate emotions, but merely acknowledged and shifted onto individual users, who are made responsible for a state of affairs they neither created nor can meaningfully affect.

Zooming in on ethics washing and critical washing

[T]he integration of AI in education represents an opportunity to improve teaching and learning processes, but it also requires an ethical and responsible approach to ensure that this technology benefits all learners in an equitable and fair manner. (SMEVTS 2024: 5)

This fragment epitomizes the type of ethics and critical washing we are especially interested in: acknowledging ethical risks without seriously considering their ethical entailments in detail, and acting upon them at the institutional level from which the call to individual responsibility is issued. What is the point of acknowledging harms and risks if one fails to act upon this realization? A defender might retort that the guideline explicitly calls for an ethical and responsible approach. In line with Suárez et al. (2025) above, we might reply that reflecting on harm does not amount to taking action against it and cannot be considered a sufficiently responsible course of action. That is precisely what the washing is about: ethical concern and calls to action as a simulacrum without ethical consequence. These performative, inconsequential calls to responsibility amount to something we have called Responsible Realism, which is a particularly insidious way of eschewing genuine responsibility. We develop this idea further in the following section.

4 Responsible Realism: when responsibility becomes self-undermining

Calls to responsibility and responsible use are ubiquitously found in the analyzed guidelines and documentation. Responsibility is positioned as both an ethical imperative and a pragmatic solution in a way that reconciles the acknowledged harms and risks with its alleged benefits.

This mechanism is encapsulated in the following fragments:

While these tools can enhance productivity and insights, their use comes with ethical responsibilities. Researchers at the Faculty of Economic Sciences, University of Warsaw, must ensure that AI is used responsibly, transparently, and with scholarly integrity. (UW n.d.)

It is therefore necessary to jointly design this new scope of opportunities to enable both the meaningful and responsible use and evaluation of AI tools in university teaching, with the purpose of enabling lecturers and students to develop comprehensive skills at the same time. (Baumhauer et al. 2024: 4)

The guidelines ostensibly, and inadmissibly in our view, place these two dimensions on the same continuum. Responsible use and responsibility are thus presented as a trade-off between the principled and the pragmatic, whereby the goal is to maximize both. But this approach hides a zero-sum game. We heed the call posed by Franklin (1999: 123) and “explore our objections in terms of principle.” In the case of AI, we therefore reject the trade-off between moral values and benefits as an admissible course of action. For what amount of money is it responsible to betray your best friend?

We see no reason to subordinate moral values to pragmatic benefits as a general practice. Granted, in some situations—like the life-and-death decisions explored in bioethics—a trade-off between moral values and benefits could be ethically admissible. However, it would be a category error to do this in situations such as the adoption of educational technologies, which do not present life-and-death quandaries or tragic choices. Nolen Gertz (2025: 32) observes,

“Bioethics was developed because even though medical practices could be dangerous, they were still necessary. But AI is dangerous without being necessary! Likening AI ethics to Bioethics gives the false impression that AI is as necessary as Medicine. So why does AI ethics help perpetuate the false impression that AI is necessary?”

The appeal to responsibility functions thus less as a genuine critical stance than as a gesture that pre-structures what is thinkable and permissible while perfunctorily acknowledging responsibility. This call to responsibility also undermines itself methodologically by committing an inconsistency known as *special pleading*. Special pleading occurs when a reasoner applies a general principle broadly but exempts a particular case that serves their interests, even though the principle clearly applies there as well (Arp et al. 2019). In the guidelines we reviewed, responsibility is routinely mandated for the use of AI, yet it is not applied to the decision to adopt AI in the first place. The inconsistency might have to do with the writers holding a deterministic view—a blind spot—that prevents them from seeing adoption as an actual choice to which the principle of responsibility also applies. Be that as it may, unless there is a relevant difference between “use” and “adoption” that warrants calling for responsible use but not for responsible adoption, which might in principle entail not adopting genAI at all, this remains a grave inconsistency.

Consider the emphasis on responsibility and responsible use present in the following fragments, more this time than above as they illustrate the umbrella term we coin, *responsible realism* (emphasis: ours):

The university promotes the **responsible** use of AI to support scientific work. (HWR 2025: 7, in German in the original)

It is the **responsibility** of all users to be aware of biases and to develop a critical awareness of them. (HWR 2025: 9, in German in the original)

KIT encourages its members, affiliates, and bodies to make broad use of the potential of generative AI in order to shape its core tasks of research, teaching, transfer, administration, and infrastructure in an innovative and sustainable manner and to assume social **responsibility**. (KIT 2025: 1, in German in the original)

GenAI encompasses a range of promising tools, which, if implemented and used **responsibly**, can boost productivity ... (Maastricht 2024: 3)

It is therefore particularly important to prepare our students to use AI **responsibly**. (Wolfgang Kersten in Baumhauer et al. 2024: 2)

With a focus on privacy-friendly innovation, **responsible** use, and robust data management, this framework offers practical steps for aligning AI applications with regulatory requirements and institutional values. (Braun 2024: 26, in German in the original)

A deterministic perspective entails compliance in adoption and use; after all, as the mantra goes, “AI is here to stay.” Faced with the inevitable, a responsible use, then, seems to be the ethically desirable course of action, and this sounds unproblematic, but is it? Admittedly, all of the cited documents acknowledge various ethical and legal problems (bias, privacy issues, erosion of critical thinking, etc.), but they also, as seen in the fragments above, highlight the incentives for the advantages that the use of generative AI may offer. The

harms and disadvantages of these technologies, however, amply outweigh the supposed advantages. Furthermore, advantages for whom?

Inspired by the notion of *Realpolitik*—a term that refers to a results-oriented approach to political decision-making grounded in practical considerations rather than *idealism*—we call this trade-off between inevitability and putative gains, on the one side, and ethics, on the other, *Responsible Realism*. The mechanism of Responsible Realism is as follows: ethical concerns are often identified and warned against throughout these documents and even explicitly characterized as deplorable and to be avoided (e.g., SMEVTS 2024; HWR 2025). Yet, the rejection or the opting-out of the current commercial technology remains unconsidered. What is more, it is promoted despite its woeful and well-known effects, as referred to above. The responsible realist’s position forecloses the possibility that AI systems can be developed and institutionally deployed in ways that are responsible in a strong sense, i.e., being more genuinely conducive to human flourishing, and to pluralistically serve human needs and democratic values.

To clarify, whereas Responsible Realism is the institutional stance, a *responsible realist* is any person who adheres to it, whether they belong to an institution or not. The responsible realist endorses principles and ideals *pro forma* but, in practice, is primarily guided by pragmatic considerations. The premise of inevitability narrows down and alters the order of the ethical questions to give primacy to pragmatic ones: instead of asking questions like “Do we need this?” or “What for, and for whom, and at what cost?” they ask “How should individuals use it responsibly?” Or, in Weizenbaum’s (1972) terms, instead of asking “Is it good?” they ask “What electronic wizardry will make [computers] safe?”

Responsible Realism consists, then, in calling upon individuals to use the technology while acknowledging its intrinsic problems and harmful effects, and insisting that those problems be mitigated through individual action at the end-user level. For example, by exhorting users to check results for bias and falsehoods. In the context of AI, the systemic nature of the harms and risks makes individual attempts at “responsible use” irremediably ineffective in addressing the underlying problems. Obviously, end users cannot solve the intrinsic problems of these tools through responsible use, which sets a low standard for responsibility.

Responsible Realism is inherently paradoxical. If we take seriously the impossibility of resisting the use of a highly practical tool that allegedly “is here to stay,” to what extent could responsible use be viable? If we accept techno-determinism and that practicality and advantages make opting out of such systems unfeasible, why would genuine responsible use be possible at all? Why call for responsibility? Our preliminary answer is that the responsible realist pursues a form of responsibility that is laden with reservations and merely carries out a strategy of legitimation that prioritizes personal, political, or economic convenience, maintains the *status quo*, and helps perpetuate inequalities and systemic problems under a discourse of responsibility. In other words, the realists want to have their cake and eat it too.

Weizenbaum (1976: 241, see quote above in Section 2) argued that inevitability serves to remove people from responsibility. However, Responsible Realism, even if also underpinned by the myth of inevitability, functions in a slightly different manner: its goal is not to disconnect people from responsibility but to enable people to embrace a watered-down form of responsibility. It’s a low-effort surrogate for ethical behavior. In addition, the focus on individual action not only neglects the relational character of both technology and good education, but also erodes it by nudging students, teachers, and others involved toward individualism. Comparing the

bench-style seating of buses in some areas of Latin America with the individual seats in European buses, Almudena Hernando (2012: 30) argues:

“It is not only that we produce individualized objects because we ourselves are individualized, but that through the routine use of these objects we become increasingly individualized, so in the future we will generate ever more individualized objects that will reinforce the logic of this social trend.”⁴

Such technological individualization is part of a much broader cultural illusion. The Western modern tradition—and particularly Neoclassical Economics—has long conceptualized humans as *Homo economicus*: a rational, calculating, and self-maximizing individual. In contrast, extensive work across anthropology, psychology, and related fields has shown that many societies conceive of persons not as bounded individuals but as “dividuals” whose intentions, experiences, and even bodies and cognition are shared, distributed, and relationally constituted (cf. Birhane 2017; Sahlins 2008). Along these lines, responsibility itself is not an attribute carried by isolated individuals but a relational achievement, something distributed across the shared purposes, obligations, and ways of being and doing that constitute education as a practice: “Neither agency nor intentionality is a simple expression of individuality, inasmuch the being of the other is an internal condition of one’s own activity” (Sahlins 2008: 49).

Responsibility can have both a prospective and retrospective sense (cf. Mele 2020: 60-65; Van de Poel 2015). In the retrospective sense, responsibility is often understood as having to do with blame or praise, as when a person is *held* responsible for having done something or for failing to act as expected. In its prospective sense, at its simplest, it can be understood as a relation between a person and a state of affairs or act, in the sense of being responsible *for* doing something. In this spirit, responsibility involves taking charge of something or a state of affairs, feeling or being obliged to act or refrain from acting, and accounting for what has been done or omitted. Both senses are not mutually exclusive and could even be applied to the same agent, as the retrospective and the prospective can be interrelated. For instance, when a person receives praise for the way they carried out an act for which they were, at the time, prospectively responsible.

Responsible Realism exploits the prospective sense in favor of institutions and companies by framing it as an individual affair and delegating it accordingly. By assigning the forward-looking duty to use AI ethically to the end users, institutions simultaneously insulate themselves from accountability for any ethical consequence of use: if things go wrong, the institution can claim it acted responsibly by recommending responsible use! This is an explicit exercise of asymmetric power, and it maps directly onto ethical washing and critical washing: the institution identifies ethical issues but stops short of acting on them, shifting the duty of care to individuals and avoiding any potential blame for harms and risks. Furthermore, tech companies’ accountability is also erased from the equation in the process.

Figure 1 shows the elements of Responsible Realism: premises, their putative entailments, the rhetorical strategies adopted, and the results of this particular form of critical washing and ethics washing that is Responsible Realism.

⁴ In Spanish in the original. Translated by the authors.

Figure 1. Elements of Responsible Realism.

An example of such a behavior arises when plagiarism ceases to be an issue worthy of unequivocal condemnation and becomes a matter of individual responsible use mediated by technology. Long considered one of the pinnacles of academic misconduct, the general excoriation of plagiarism is dissolved because it is not exercised in first person anymore but delegated to a machine. As teachers, we never accepted work fully or partially prepared by a third-party such as a student's colleague or an essay-writing service, as that constituted plagiarism—or collusion, also a serious form of academic misconduct. Yet, and this is not a defense of traditional assignments per se, it now turns out that some find it admissible to accept an assignment produced wholly or partially by a machine as long as the student is responsible for the prompt and the output. We wonder: *did students who wanted to cheat not have to prompt their colleagues or representatives of essay-writing services before?* Be that as it may, for the responsible realists, the responsibility not to cheat lies with the student⁵ and not with the institutions, which instead of providing clear guidance on the matter and upholding their commitment to the student's learning process, allow or facilitate the use of a machine whose primary operating mechanism is combining and regurgitating earlier texts in a way that can be detrimental to actual learning. Nor does it lie with the companies that have designed and developed those features.

Genuine responsibility might thus entail—and we posit that it does in this case—accepting that you can't have it both ways. If universities accept that generative AI is based on discriminatory, extractivist, biased, illegal, and unethical practices as many scholars argue (see e.g. Guest et al. forthcoming, cf. Section 1) and the many ethical and legal issues that institutions themselves acknowledge in their own documents, then they *must* commit and make a choice. Namely, either they abandon the calls to responsible use, or *walk the walk*—and not just *talk the talk*—by embracing a principled rejection of the current commercial technologies, or at least by explicitly recognizing opting out as a legitimate course of action for faculty members, administrative staff,

⁵ Let us be clear: we have always believed, and still do, that most students want to learn and have no desire to cheat.

and students—a proposal we return to below. Continuing to call for the responsible use of a technology, the use and development of which is fraught with socio-economic, environmental, political, and ethical harms, it is not only paradoxical but self-undermining.

We are not taking a maximalist stance here. Would we call it responsible to buy and use a shirt made under exploitative labor conditions simply because it is elegant and cheap? No. We might *understand* and even find this kind of consumption admissible by pointing to the lack of viable alternatives that many people have or the constraints imposed by market conditions and low wages, but it would make no sense to describe such behavior as responsible simply because one is aware of the systemic human-rights abuses in the global supply chains.

Following Hannah Arendt (2003), we posit that genuinely responsible use requires thinking critically and resisting the acceptance of systems that perpetuate harm, as well as rejecting the rhetorics and narratives that impede critical and ethical reasoning. For responsible use, it is not enough to acknowledge harms while promoting the very technologies that are imbricated with those harms. Vapid calls to responsible use are merely rationalizations meant to ease the emotional burden of cognitive dissonance and will remain inconsequential. What we have termed Responsible Realism dilutes the concept of responsibility, normalizes injustice, and shifts the ethical burden—at least an important part of it—onto users instead of institutions or companies, who are the ones expected to take charge or be accountable. Reflecting on how the mechanisms of social life press individuals in certain directions in spite of their own orientations, Charles Taylor (1991: 8) sketches clear limits for what can be achieved individually:

“Our degrees of freedom are not zero. There is a point to deliberating what ought to be our ends, and whether instrumental reason ought to have a lesser role in our lives than it does. But the truth in these analyses is that it is not just a matter of changing the outlook of individuals, it is not just a battle of ‘hearts and minds,’ important as this is. Change in this domain will have to be institutional as well ...”

Education and its systemic issues require collective solutions that lie beyond the individual responsibility of end users, as the cases of the climate emergency or slave labor in the garment industry teach us. The problems we have identified arise from institutional structures and socio-technical conditions, not from the behavior of individual students or teachers. It is precisely on these grounds that the Responsible Realism underpinning university guidelines and similar documents for the use of (generative) AI must be rejected.

5 Conclusions

We don't claim to have offered in this essay sufficient grounds for a blanket rejection of the technologies that make up the ecosystem of AI-based educational tools. Nor do we suggest having offered an exhaustive or comprehensive summary of objections or problems that can be encountered in university guidelines. As we stated at the beginning, our aim was to identify, name, and develop the notion of Responsible Realism as a critical lens with which to expose the contradictions and paradoxes underlying the rhetorical architecture of a set of tropes and wrongheaded claims made by institutions and corporations about the nature, capacities, and ethical status of generative AI systems, as well as to identify and reject the false dilemmas and trade-offs that form part of that architecture. We hope the concept of Responsible Realism is robust and our critical argument sufficiently persuasive, but since we aim for our argument to be constructive as well, we want to end by sketching some proposals for both universities and teachers.

Firstly, universities can be genuinely responsible by not offloading the problem onto teachers, students, and researchers, among others, but instead by leading. Secondly, they can be responsible by resisting the industry-driven narratives we have criticized here, and instead by using their structural power to safeguard the conditions under which education and science can function as public goods. Paradoxically, this could be achieved not necessarily by doing but by *refraining from doing*, that is, by refraining from promoting and normalizing harmful technologies and unethical practices, and making them *de facto* acceptable.

Thirdly, another course of action for universities could be to actively promote and foster an open, participatory space for the whole university community that, without ignoring the reality of AI use, does not take it as a *fait accompli*. This entails posing first, albeit somewhat belatedly, the “question zero” of whether the institutional adoption of AI *ought* to occur and simultaneously for what purpose. Only then, eventually, how it can happen. Mitigating risks and harms is paramount, and offering best practices is useful, but the purposes and conditions of any eventual adoption must be debated and not taken as an unknown given. At least, institutions must create and endorse protected spaces for those who wish to opt out of technologies that are institutionally deployed and assumed to be adopted. Faculty members, staff, and students should be able to do so without this “imposing a burden on them or negatively affecting their working or learning conditions” (AAUP 2025).

Furthermore, universities must apply the critical thinking and the responsibility they preach and reject trade-offs between incommensurable values. Why must we accept being compelled to choose between efficiency and supporting students in becoming autonomous and genuinely responsible? Universities do not actually need to choose between convenience and fairness; these are false choices encouraged by the industry’s marketing hype (Guest et al. forthcoming; Bender and Hanna 2025) and the sense of urgency created by the vertiginous rates of adoption. The institutional adoption of AI is not comparable to medical triage, where medical staff, due to the situational time conditions in which they find themselves, are tremendously constrained to choose between substantial goods to which they are committed. Adopting ChatGPT is nothing like choosing who will get a ventilator during a pandemic and who will not. The trade-offs between values that cannot all be satisfied at once might be permissible because of necessity and time pressure, but must be rejected when other choices are available, as in this case. Ventilators are necessary; ChatGPT and Copilot are not.

Responsibility does impose demands on the rest of us *qua* teachers as well, of course, but of a different nature. Even in the most difficult circumstances, it is possible to engage critically with generative AI and think for ourselves. It is our responsibility to reject narratives that normalize supposed technological inevitabilities to place the onus back where it belongs. Institutions have the responsibility for creating the conditions in which the reflexive and deliberative practices required for responsible technological governance can occur. Yet, deterministic narratives are ideological instruments that, under the guise of achieving institutional preparedness, can erode our collective agency and hinder principled debate by presenting human-made software artefacts as if they were the unavoidable results of natural forces instead of products of human practices and decisions embedded in socio-political contexts. This surreptitiously nudges those in academic communities towards helplessness and resignation, thus discouraging deliberation, discernment, and contestation.

Fighting our own thoughtlessness is the first step towards genuine individual responsibility, even—or especially—when we are constantly being primed by our own institutions to accept technology as an

autonomous force, are enchanted with the empty promise of effortless productivity, and threatened with the label of being a technophobe or luddite, a severe social stigma placed on someone who defies the fallacious orthodoxy that equates technological progress with the good, or who doubts its supposed future benefits without accounting for the present harms. To break the enchantment, we as educators, together with the academic community as a whole, which includes administration, staff, students, and regulators, must fight to preserve the capacity to ask questions of purpose: not only about what AI technologies are good *at*, but also about what are they *for*, and *why* we would want them in our classrooms and labs and under what conditions.

Ursula Franklin (1999: 123) reminds us,

“When, on the basis of principled objections, an established social practice has become less and less acceptable, then, and maybe only then, will alternatives be found. From then on tasks that need to be done will be carried out differently and by more acceptable means.”

Other AI technologies, different from the commercially available ones we have now, are possible—maybe less “revolutionary,” less “game-changing,” less “groundbreaking,” but also less exploitative, more democratic and fairer, and more hospitable to our flourishing as teachers and students. It should be up to us to decide whether, how, and for what we use them. Yet, for these alternatives to be found we must reject and ridicule exaggerated, implausible narratives first. Especially, we must not succumb to the defeatism, resignation, and passivity that determinism and enchantment attempt to inculcate, nor to a “responsible realism” that merely soothes our conscience while the harms, risks, and injustices continue as if they were inevitable trade-offs that we must accept, because they are not. And we must not.

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References

- AAUP. 2025. “Artificial Intelligence and Academic Professions.” Report, Committee on Artificial Intelligence and Academic Professions, *American Association of University Professors*. <https://www.aaup.org/reports-publications/aaup-policies-reports/topical-reports/artificial-intelligence-and-academic>
- Ajuzieogu, Uchechukwu. 2025, August 31. “The Mind Miners: How Silicon Valley’s AI Gold Rush is Built on African Trauma.” *Aylgorith*. <https://aylgorith.com/mind-miners-ai-trauma/>
- Akingbola, Adewunmi; Adeleke, Oluwatimilehin; Idris, Ayotomiwa; Adewole, Olajumoke; Adegbesan, Abiodun. 2024. “Artificial intelligence and the dehumanization of patient care.” *Journal of Medicine, Surgery, and Public Health* 3, 100138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gjmedi.2024.100138>
- Arendt, Hanna. 2003. *Responsibility and judgment*. Schocken Books.
- Arp, Robert; Barbone, Steven; Bruce, Michael (eds.). 2019. *Bad arguments: 100 of the most important fallacies in Western philosophy*. Wiley-Blackwell.
- Baumhauer, Maren; Bulmann, Ulrike; Watolla, Ann-Kathrin. 2024. “AI-Tools for Teaching and Learning: Guidance from TU Hamburg.” *Technische Universität Hamburg*. <https://doi.org/10.15480/882.13389>

- Bender, Emily M. 2024. "Resisting dehumanization in the age of "AI"." *Current Directions in Psychological Science* 33(2):114–120. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09637214231217286>
- Bender, Emily M.; Hanna, Alex. 2025. *The AI Con: How to Fight Big Tech's Hype and Create the Future We Want*. Harper.
- Benedetti, Paul; Nancy DeHart, eds. 1997. *Forward Through the Rearview Mirror: Reflections on and by Marshall McLuhan*. MIT Press.
- Benjamin, Ruha. 2019. *Race after technology: Abolitionist tools for the new Jim Code*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Bietti, Elettra. 2021. "From Ethics Washing to Ethics Bashing: A Moral Philosophy View on Tech Ethics." *Journal of Social Computing* 2(3):266–283. <https://doi.org/10.23919/JSC.2021.0031>
- Bijker, Wiebe E.; Hughes, Thomas P.; Pinch, Trevor (Eds.). 1987. *The social construction of technological systems: New directions in the sociology and history of technology*. MIT Press.
- Birhane, Abeba. 2017, April 7. "Descartes Was Wrong: 'A Person Is a Person through Other Persons'." *Aeon*. <https://aeon.co/ideas/descartes-was-wrong-a-person-is-a-person-through-other-persons>
- Birhane, Abeba. 2023. "Algorithmic colonization of Africa." In Stephen Cave & Kanta Dihal (eds.), *Imagining AI: How the World Sees Intelligent Machines*, 247–260, Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780192865366.003.0016>
- Birhane, Abeba; Dehdashtian, Sepehr; Prabhu, Vinay; Boddeti Vishnu. 2024. "The Dark Side of Dataset Scaling: Evaluating Racial Classification in Multimodal Models." In *Proceedings of the 2024 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, FAccT '24, 1229-1244. Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3630106.3658968>
- Braun, Alexander. 2024. "TUM AI Strategy" (Original: "TUM KI Strategie"). *Technische Universität München*. <https://mediatum.ub.tum.de/1766632>
- Brignull, Harry; Leiser, Mark; Santos, Cristina; Doshi, Kosha. 2023. "Deceptive patterns – user interfaces designed to trick you." *deceptive.design*. <https://www.deceptive.design>
- Caulfield, Mike. 2025, May 9. "AI Is Not Your Friend: How the 'opinionated' chatbots destroyed AI's potential, and how we can fix it." *The Atlantic*. <https://www.theatlantic.com/technology/archive/2025/05/sycophantic-ai/682743/>
- Chen, Angelina Ying; Koegel, Sarah Isabel; Hannon, Oliver; Ciriello, Raffaele. 2023. "Feels Like Empathy: How "Emotional" AI Challenges Human Essence." *ACIS 2023 Proceedings* 80. <https://aisel.aisnet.org/acis2023/80>
- Council EU. 2023. "Asbestos: Council and Parliament strike deal on new rules protecting workers." *Council of the European Union*. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2023/06/27/asbestos-council-and-parliament-strike-deal-on-new-rules-protecting-workers/>
- Dang, Jianning; Liu, Li. 2025 "Dehumanization risks associated with artificial intelligence use." *American Psychologist*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0001542>
- De Freitas Netto, Sebastião Vieira; Falcão Sobral, Marcos Felipe; Bezerra Ribeiro, Ana Regina; da Luz Soares, Gleibson Robert. 2020. "Concepts and forms of greenwashing: a systematic review." *Environmental Sciences Europe* 32, 19: 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-020-0300-3>
- Dennett, Daniel. 1989. *The intentional stance*. MIT Press.

- Epley, Nicholas; Waytz, Adam; Cacioppo, John T. 2007. "On seeing human: A three-factor theory of anthropomorphism." *Psychological Review* 114(4):864–886. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295X.114.4.864>
- Eubanks, Virginia. 2019. *Automating inequality: How high-tech tools profile, police, and punish the poor*. St. Martin's Press.
- EU. 2022. "Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market for Digital Services and Amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act)." *Official Journal of the European Union* L 277:1–102. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32022R2065>
- FBI. 2024, December 3. "Criminals Use Generative Artificial Intelligence to Facilitate Financial Fraud. Alert Number: I-120324-PSA." *Federal Bureau of Investigation, USA*. <https://www.ic3.gov/PSA/2024/PSA241203>
- Feenberg, Andrew. 1999. *Questioning technology*. Routledge.
- Fergusson, Grant; Geoghegan, Sara; Schroeder, Calli; Villegas Bravo, Maria. 2024. "Generating harms: Generative AI's new & continued impacts." *Electronic Privacy Information Center*. <https://epic.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/EPIC-Generative-AI-II-Report-May2024-1.pdf>
- Flenady, Gene; Sparrow, Robert. 2025. "Cut the bullshit: why GenAI systems are neither collaborators nor tutors." *Teaching in Higher Education*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562517.2025.2497263>
- Flyvbjerg, Bent. 2006. "Five Misunderstandings About Case-Study Research." *Qualitative Inquiry*, 12(2), 219–245. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10778004052843>
- Forbes, Samuel H.; Guest, Olivia. 2025. "To Improve Literacy, Improve Equality in Education, Not Large Language Models." *Cognitive Science* 49(4):e70058. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cogs.70058>
- Frank, Arthur L.; van Zandwijk, Nico. 2024. "Asbestos history and use." *Lung Cancer* 193:107828. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lungcan.2024.107828>
- Franklin, Ursula. 1999. *The Real World of Technology*. Toronto: House of Anansi Press.
- Gerdes, Anne. 2022. "The tech industry hijacking of the AI ethics research agenda and why we should reclaim it." *Discover Artificial Intelligence* 2:25. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44163-022-00043-3>
- Gertz, Nolen. 2025, March 19. "Why AI Ethics Is Unethical." *MHeNs Annual Research Day*, Maastricht. <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/63f3978fa407756fef75412f/t/67e01a471328da7c99f5ff05/1742740057233/Why+AI+Ethics+is+Unethical+-+Maastricht.pdf>
- Goetze, T. S. 2024. "AI Art is Theft: Labour, Extraction, and Exploitation, Or, On the Dangers of Stochastic Pollocks." In *Proceedings of the 2024 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, FAccT'24, 186–196. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3630106.3658898>
- Guersenzvaig, Ariel; Sánchez-Monedero, Javier. 2025. "AI research assistants, intrinsic values, and the science we want." *AI & Society* 40:235–237. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-023-01861-4>
- Guersenzvaig, Ariel; Sánchez-Monedero, Javier; Gopegui, Belén; Picassó i Piquer, Maria. Forthcoming. "Inteligencia artificial generativa en la educación universitaria: la urgencia de una perspectiva crítica" (Original: "Generative artificial intelligence in higher education: the urgency of a critical perspective"). *Daimon*, Revista Internacional de Filosofía. <https://revistas.um.es/daimon/libraryFiles/downloadPublic/17851>
- Guest, Olivia; Suárez, Marcela; Müller, Barbara; van Meerkerk, Edwin; Oude Groote Beverborg, Arnoud; de Haan, Ronald; Reyes Elizondo, Andrea; Blokpoel, Mark; Scharfenberg, Natalia; Kleinherenbrink, Annelies;

Camerino, Ileana; Woensdregt, Marieke; Monett, Dagmar; Brown, Jed; Avraamidou, Lucy; Alenda-Demoutiez, Juliette; Hermans, Feliene; van Rooij, Iris. Forthcoming. Against the Uncritical Adoption of 'AI' Technologies in Academia. *Journal of Digital Culture & Education*.

Hao, Karen. 2025. *Empire of AI: Dreams and Nightmares in Sam Altman's OpenAI*. Penguin Press.

Hao, Karen; Seetharaman, Deepa. 2023, July 24. "Cleaning up ChatGPT takes heavy toll on human workers." *The Wall Street Journal*. <https://www.wsj.com/articles/chatgpt-openai-content-abusive-sexually-explicit-harassment-kenya-workers-on-human-workers-cf191483>

Hartzog, Woodrow; Silbey, Jessica M. 2025. "How AI Destroys Institutions." *77 UC Law Journal* (forthcoming 2026), Boston Univ. School of Law Research Paper No. 5870623. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5870623>

Hernando, Almudena. 2012. *La fantasía de la individualidad* (engl. "The fantasy of individuality"). Fabricantes de sueños.

Hill, Kashmir; Valentino-DeVries, Jennifer. 2025, November 23. "What OpenAI did when ChatGPT users lost touch with reality." *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2025/11/23/technology/openai-chatgpt-users-risks.html>

Hofstadter, Douglas. 1995. "Preface 4: The Ineradicable Eliza Effect and Its Dangers." In *Fluid Concepts and Creative Analogies: Computer Models of the Fundamental Mechanisms of Thought*, Basic Books: New York.

Hughes, Thomas P. 1994. "Technological Momentum." In Smith, M. R. and Marx, L. (eds.), *Does Technology Drive History? The Dilemma of Technological Determinism*, MIT Press.

HWR. 2025. "Guideline of the Berlin School of Economics and Law for the use of artificial intelligence" (Original: "Richtlinie der Hochschule für Wirtschaft und Recht Berlin für die Nutzung von Künstlicher Intelligenz"). *Mitteilungsblatt / Bulletin 61/2025*, Berlin School of Economics and Law. https://www.hwr-berlin.de/fileadmin/portal/Dokumente/HWR-Berlin/Mitteilungsbl%C3%A4tter/2025/Mitteilungsblatt_61-2025_ZHV_Richtlinie_KI_Nutzung.pdf

IEU. 2023. "Institutional Statement on Artificial Intelligence." *IE University*. <https://docs.ie.edu/IE-University-Statement-on-AI.pdf>

Ihde, Don. 1990. *Technology and the lifeworld: From garden to earth*. Indiana University Press.

ITU. n.d. "How to benefit from generative Artificial Intelligence." *IT University of Copenhagen*. <https://itustudent.itu.dk/Study-Administration/Generative-AI>

Jiménez Arandia, Pablo. 2025, March 7. "Deciphering AI Water Consumption: How Amazon Hides How Much Water Its Cloud Consumes in Spain." *El País*. <https://pulitzercenter.org/stories/deciphering-ai-water-consumption-how-amazon-hides-how-much-water-its-cloud-consumes-spain>

Kim, Hye-young; McGill, Ann L. 2024. "AI-induced dehumanization." *Journal of Consumer Psychology* 35(3):363–381. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcpy.1441>

KIT. 2025. "Guidelines for the use of generative AI at KIT" (Original: "Leitlinien zum Einsatz generativer KI am KIT"). *Karlsruhe Institut für Technologie*. <https://www.kit.edu/downloads/KI-Leitlinien-de.pdf>

Köbis, Nils; Rahwan, Zoe; Rilla, Raluca; Supriyatno, Bramantyo Ibrahim; Bersch, Ajaj, Tamer; Bonnefon, Jean-François; Rahwan, Iyad. 2025. "Delegation to artificial intelligence can increase dishonest behaviour." *Nature* 646:126–134. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-09505-x>

- Köppe, Christian; Keuning, Hieke; Lykourantzou, Ioanna; Alpízar Chacón, Isaac; Sosnovsky, Sergey. 2024. "Practices for the Application of Generative AI in Programming Education." *Utrecht University*. <https://www.uu.nl/sites/default/files/GenAI%20in%20ProgEd%20practices.pdf>
- KUDK. n.d. "AI and teaching – what are the implications?" *University of Copenhagen*. <https://obl.ku.dk/theme/ai-and-teaching/>
- Laird, Elizabeth; Dwyer, Maddy; Quay-de-la-vallee, Hannah. 2025. "Hand in Hand: Schools' Embrace of AI Connected to Increased Risks to Students." *Center for Democracy and Technology*. <https://cdt.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/FINAL-CDT-2025-Hand-in-Hand-Polling-100225-accessible.pdf>
- Latour, Bruno. 1987. *Science in action: How to follow scientists and engineers through society*. Harvard University Press.
- Luccioni, Sasha; Jernite, Yacine; Strubell, Emma. 2024. "Power Hungry Processing: Watts Driving the Cost of AI Deployment?" In *Proceedings of the 2024 ACM Conference on Fairness Accountability and Transparency, FAccT '24*, 85–99. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3630106.3658542>
- Maastricht. 2024, December. "Policy Framework Generative Artificial Intelligence". *Maastricht University*. <https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/file/policy-framework-generative-artificial-intelligence-12-12-2024pdf>
- MacKenzie, Donald; Wajcman, Judy (Eds.). 1999. *The social shaping of technology* (2nd ed.). Open University Press.
- McLuhan, Marshall; Fiore, Quentin. 1967. *The medium is the message: An inventory of effects*. Penguin Books.
- McQuillan, Dan. 2023, June 6. "Predicted benefits, proven harms: How AI's algorithmic violence emerged from our own social matrix." *The Sociological Review*. <https://thesociologicalreview.org/magazine/june-2023/artificial-intelligence/predicted-benefits-proven-harms/>
- Mejías, Ulises A.; Couldry, Nick. 2024. *Data grab: The new colonialism of big tech and how to fight back*. The University of Chicago Press.
- Melé, Domènec. 2020. *Business ethics in action* (2nd ed.). Red Globe Press.
- Metzinger, Thomas. 2019, April 8. "EU guidelines: Ethics washing made in Europe." *Tagesspiegel*. <https://www.tagesspiegel.de/politik/ethics-washing-made-in-europe-5937028.html>
- Monett, Dagmar, Grigorescu, Bogdan. 2024. "Deconstructing the AI Myth: Fallacies and Harms of Algorithmification." *Proceedings of the 23rd European Conference on e-Learning, ECEL 2024*, 23(1):242–248, Academic Conferences International Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.34190/ecel.23.1.2759>
- Monett, Dagmar; Paquet, Gilbert. 2025. "Against the Commodification of Education — if harms then not AI." *Journal of Open, Distance, and Digital Education* 2(1):1–24. <https://doi.org/10.25619/wazgw457>
- Muldoon, James; Graham, Mark; Cant, Callum. 2024. *Feeding the machine: The hidden human labor powering A.I.* Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Noble, David F. 1984. *Forces of production: A social history of industrial automation*. Oxford University Press.
- Ochigame, Rodrigo. 2019. "The Invention of 'Ethical AI': How Big Tech Manipulates Academia to Avoid Regulation." *The Intercept*. <https://theintercept.com/2019/12/20/mit-ethical-ai-artificial-intelligence/>

- OpenAI. n.d. "Customizing Your ChatGPT Personality." *OpenAI*. <https://help.openai.com/en/articles/11899719-customizing-your-chatgpt-personality>
- OpenAI. 2023. "Teaching with AI: How teachers are using ChatGPT & example prompts to get you started." *OpenAI*. <https://openai.com/index/teaching-with-ai/>
- OpenAI. 2025. "AI Communication Toolkit." *OpenAI Academy*. <https://academy.openai.com/public/clubs/higher-education-05x4z/resources/ai-communication-toolkit>
- Park, Peter S.; Goldstein, Simon; O’Gara, Aidan; Chen, Michael; Hendrycks, Dan. 2024. "AI deception: A survey of examples, risks, and potential solutions." *Patterns* 5(5):100988. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2024.100988>
- Parshley, Lois. 2024, June 20. "The Hidden Environmental Impact of AI." *Jacobin*. <https://jacobin.com/2024/06/ai-data-center-energy-usage-environment>
- Postman, Neil. 1995. *The End of Education: Redefining the Value of School*. New York: Vintage Books.
- Sahlins, Marshall. 2008. *The Western Illusion of Human Nature: With Reflections on the Long History of Hierarchy, Equality, and the Sublimation of Anarchy in the West, and Comparative Notes on Other Conceptions of the Human Condition*. Prickly Paradigm Press.
- Schroeder, Juliana; Epley, Nicholas. 2016. "Mistaking Minds and Machines: How Speech Affects Dehumanization and Anthropomorphism." *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General* 145(11):1427–1437. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xge0000214>
- Simon, Judith. 2025. "Generative AI, Quadruple Deception & Trust." *Social Epistemology* 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02691728.2025.2491087>
- Slater, Kailyn "Kay". 2025. "Against AI: Critical Refusal in the Library." *Library Trends* 73(4):588–608. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1353/lib.2025.a968497>
- SMEVTS. 2024. "Guide on the use of artificial intelligence in education." *Spanish Ministry of Education, Vocational Training and Sports & Spanish National Institute of Educational Technologies and Teacher Training*, Government of Spain. https://code.intef.es/wp-content/uploads/2025/11/Guide-on-the-use-of-artificial-intelligence-in-education_INTEF_2024.pdf
- Suárez, Marcela; Müller, Barbara C.N.; Guest, Olivia; van Rooij, Iris (2025). "Critical AI Literacy: Beyond hegemonic perspectives on sustainability." *Sustainability Dispatch*. <https://rcsc.substack.com/p/critical-ai-literacy-beyond-hegemonic>
- Tarsney, Christian. 2025. "Deception and manipulation in generative AI." *Philosophical Studies* 182:1865–1887. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11098-024-02259-8>
- Taylor, Charles. 1991. *The malaise of modernity*. House of Anansi Press.
- Turkle, Sherry. 1984. *The second self: computers and the human spirit*. Simon & Schuster, Inc.
- UOS. 2025. "Recommendations for the Use of AI-based Applications" (Original: "Recommendations for dealing with AI-based applications"). *Universität Osnabrück*. <https://www.uni-osnabrueck.de/virtuos/lehren-und-lernen/ki-in-studium-und-lehre/handlungsempfehlungen-zum-umgang-mit-ki-basierten-anwendungen>

- USEPA. 2024. "Biden-Harris Administration finalises ban on ongoing uses of asbestos to protect people from cancer." *U.S. Environmental Protection Agency*. <https://www.epa.gov/newsreleases/biden-harris-administration-finalizes-ban-ongoing-uses-asbestos-protect-people-cancer>
- UW. n.d. "Responsible Use of AI." *University of Warsaw*. <https://www.wne.uw.edu.pl/en/research/research/responsible-use-ai>
- Vallor, Shannon. 2024. *The AI Mirror: How to Reclaim Our Humanity in an Age of Machine Thinking*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Van de Poel, Ibo. 2015. "Moral responsibility." In Ibo Van de Poel, Lamber Royakkers, & Sabine D. Zwart (eds.), *Moral responsibility and the problem of many hands* (pp. 12–49). Routledge.
- Van Rooij, I.; Guest, O.; Adolphi, F.; de Haan, Ronald; Kolokolova, Antonina; Rich, Patricia. 2024. "Reclaiming AI as a Theoretical Tool for Cognitive Science." *Computational Brain & Behavior* 7:616–636. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42113-024-00217-5>
- Véliz, Carisa. 2023. "Chatbots shouldn't use emojis." *Nature* 615, 375. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-023-00758-y>
- Verbeek, Peter-Paul. 2011. *Moralizing technology: Understanding and designing the morality of things*. University of Chicago Press.
- Wagner, Ben. 2019. "Ethics As An Escape From Regulation. From 'Ethics-Washing' To Ethics-Shopping?" In Emre Bayamlioglu, Irina Baraliuc, Liisa Albertha Wilhelmina Janssens and Mireille Hildebrandt (eds.), *BEING PROFILED: COGITAS ERGO SUM: COGITAS ERGO SUM: 10 Years of Profiling the European Citizen*, pp. 84–89, Amsterdam University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9789048550180-016>
- Watermeyer, Richard; Phipps, Lawrie; Lanclos, Donna; Knight, Kathryn. 2024. "Generative AI and the Automating of Academia." *Postdigital Science and Education* 6:446–466. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42438-023-00440-6>
- Watters, Audrey. 2021. *Teaching Machines: The History of Personalized Learning*. The MIT Press.
- Waytz, Adam; Morewedge, Carey K.; Epley, Nicholas; Monteleone, George; Gao, Jia-Hong; Cacioppo, John T. 2010. "Making sense by making sentient: Effectance motivation increases anthropomorphism." *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 99(3):410–435. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0020240>
- Weizenbaum, Joseph. 1972. "On the Impact of the Computer on Society." *Science* 176, 609–614. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.176.4035.609>
- Weizenbaum, Joseph. 1976. *Computer Power and Human Reason: From judgment to calculation*. Penguin Books.
- Whittaker, Meredith. 2021. "The steep cost of capture." *interactions* 28(6):50–55. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3488666>
- Wieczorek, Michał; Hosseini, Mohammad; Gordijn, Bert. 2025. "Unpacking the ethics of using AI in primary and secondary education: a systematic literature review." *AI Ethics* 5:4693–4711. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-025-00770-0>
- Wilkins, Joe. 2025. "The AI Industry Is Traumatizing Desperate Contractors in the Developing World for Pennies." *Futurism*. <https://futurism.com/artificial-intelligence/ai-industry-traumatizing-contractors>

Williamson, Ben; Molnar, Alex; Boninger, Faith. 2024. "Time for a pause: Without effective public oversight, AI in schools will do more harm than good." *National Education Policy Center*.
<https://nepc.colorado.edu/publication/ai>